

Design and Fabrication of Tree Plantation Machine

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ABSTRACT

Tree planting involves the transplantation of tree seedlings, typically for purposes such as forestry, land reclamation, or landscaping, setting it apart from arboriculture's larger tree transplantation and the slower, less reliable distribution of tree seeds[1]. Efficient regeneration methods are crucial for sustainable forestry to ensure the rapid establishment of new forests. In India, manual planting accounts for 95% of efforts, but the challenge lies in finding labour for this demanding task. Addressing industry needs, an autonomous scarifying and planting machine with precision, low environmental impact, and a favourable work environment has been developed and tested over two years by a collaborative group comprising researchers, manufacturers, and the Karnataka Forest Department[5]. This project encompasses various subsystems, including regeneration and route planning, autonomous driving (path planning), low-impact forest regeneration technology, automatic plant management, crane motion planning, planting spot detection, and follow-up procedures. Each subsystem underwent individual testing before integration during field trials at a clear-cut site. Notably, the concept has demonstrated significant environmental benefits, reducing soil disturbances from approximately 50% (via disc trenching) to less than 3%. The Auto plant project highlights challenges and opportunities for future development, such as balancing machine cost and operating speed, ensuring sensor reliability under vibrations and adverse weather conditions, and enhancing precision in obstacle detection during autonomous operations.

Keywords – Tree planting, forestry, route planning, regeneration, Auto plant.

1. Introduction

A tree plantation, also known as a forest plantation, timber plantation, or tree farm, refers to a forest specifically planted for the efficient production of wood on a large scale, typically by cultivating a single type of tree as a monoculture forest. The term "tree farm" is also applied to tree nurseries and Christmas tree farms. Plantation forestry is designed to yield a high volume of wood within a relatively short timeframe. These plantations are established by various entities, including state forestry authorities like the Forestry Commission in Britain, as well as the paper and wood industries, and private landowners such as Weyerhaeuser, Rayonier, and Sierra Pacific Industries in the United States, or Asia Pulp & Paper in Indonesia. Plantations are also commonly used for growing Christmas trees, while teak plantations have become prevalent in parts of southern and southeastern Asia, often replacing natural forests. These industrial plantations are meticulously managed to ensure efficient commercial production of forest products. The machine is designed to operate autonomously or with operator assistance, with a primary focus on significantly enhancing the speed and precision of tree planting operations. It aims to improve the efficiency of tree planting by leveraging technological advancements. The machine's adaptability to diverse & harsh environmental conditions is a key feature, ensuring its effectiveness in various ecosystems. By automating labour-intensive tasks associated with traditional tree planting, the machine not only reduces the demand for human labor but also enhances precision and success rates.

2. Literature Review

Linnea J. Hansson et al (2024): To expedite the development of new forests, sustainable forestry relies on efficient regeneration methods. In Sweden, nearly all planting activities rely on physical labour, despite challenges in securing sufficient labour. An autonomous solution capable of precise planting and scarification, with minimal environmental impact and providing a comfortable work environment, is highly sought after in the forestry sector. Over the past two years, researchers, manufacturers, and forest companies have collaborated on a groundbreaking initiative known as Auto plant, aimed at autonomous forest regeneration. This innovative concept integrates various subsystems including regeneration planning, autonomous driving, advanced technology for environmentally friendly regeneration, automated plant management, crane motion planning, planting spot detection, and post-planting follow-up.

The individual subsystems underwent rigorous testing, culminating in a field test at a clearcut site where they were seamlessly integrated. Auto plant shows tremendous promise, particularly in its environmental impact, as evidenced by the significant reduction in soil disturbances, dropping from approximately 50% with traditional disc trenching to less than 3%. However, the project also highlights several challenges and opportunities for further development. These include optimizing the balance between machine cost and operational speed, ensuring sensor robustness in varying weather conditions and against vibrations, and enhancing obstacle detection accuracy during autonomous operations. These considerations are critical for advancing the Auto plant concept and its potential contributions to sustainable forestry practices [1].

Jussi Manner, Back Tomas Ersson (2021): As manual labour for tree planting becomes increasingly scarce in Nordic forestry, the costs associated with regeneration are on the rise. While existing intermittently advancing tree planting machines deliver commendable silvicultural outcomes, their operational expenses remain high due to limited productivity. Conversely, continuously advancing planting machines, renowned for their heightened efficiencies, are now seen as a viable solution to mitigate escalating regeneration costs. The Silva Nova, a historically significant continuously advancing tree planting machine, boasted impressive productivity. However, its drawbacks included substantial labour requirements, necessitating two operators, and the arbitrary selection of planting locations. In contrast, the Super Silva represents a conceptual leap forward in modernizing the Silva Nova, integrating automation and microsite identification to enhance operational efficiency. Utilizing discrete-event simulation, we assessed the stocking rate and spatial distribution of tree planting using the Super Silva. The simulation outcomes revealed that integrating sensors for identifying suitable microsites enables continuously advancing planting machines like the Super Silva to plant seedlings in a manner that is both numerically and spatially optimal, particularly on moraine soils. Consequently, the incorporation of such sensors would elevate the competitiveness and adaptability of tree planting machinery.

However, the current limitation lies in the unavailability of reliable and robust sensor technology that can withstand diverse operating conditions. As such, future advancements in sensor technology are crucial to fully harnessing the potential of continuously advancing planting machines for sustainable forestry practices [2].

Dagnija Lazdina et al (2019): The mounding soil preparation method, with variations in pit depth and mound height, presents a potential solution for establishing new forests in regions with unfavourable soil water regimes. This approach utilizes the pit as a water reservoir during rainy periods, retaining moisture that can sustain seedlings through dry seasons. Seedlings planted on mounds can access water through the capillary system within the soil, enhancing their survival and growth prospects. With the increasing occurrence of extreme weather conditions in recent decades and challenges like labour shortages and rising hourly labour costs, mechanized planting on mounds emerges as a promising strategy to advance tree planting practices, particularly in Latvia. This study aimed to compare the productivity, quality, and cost-effectiveness of mechanized planting versus manual planting in Latvian conditions, where planting densities of 2-2.5 thousand seedlings per hectare are common. The M-planter was chosen for mechanized

establishment on mounded soils. Field trials involving the planting of 2000 trees per hectare revealed that the M-planter achieved productivity rates of 11.2 hours per hectare on drained peat soils, 11.6 hours per hectare on drained mineral soils, and 14.1 hours per hectare on wet mineral soils. On average, mechanized planting required 11.9 hours per hectare, while the combined process of mound creation and manual planting took 11.2 hours per hectare.

The cost of mechanized planting experiments in Latvian conditions varied between 450 and 550 EUR per hectare, depending on the number of seedlings planted and the specific planting conditions. Notably, tree establishment success did not significantly differ between sites where seedlings were planted using mechanized or manual methods, highlighting the importance of local site conditions in determining overall success rates [3].

Olimpia PANDIA et.al 2014: The section is equipped with a transmission mechanism for several elements, including pot bearers. These bearers maintain a constant vertical position relative to the slope of the terrain. They receive rotational movement via a Gall chain from a wheel that mimics the soil's movement, allowing for the adjustment of plant spacing within rows. This section can be integrated into a seedling planting machine designed for pots in 1–2 rows on terrain covered with foil mulch or in 1–6 rows on uncovered terrain. Additionally, it can serve as part of an agricultural implement for soil processing, mounting foil mulch, or installing watering hoses. The transmission system from the copy wheel enables adjustments in revolutions to vary row spacing, while the pot bearer elements offer flexibility in length adjustments for the same purpose [4].

Mohammed Amer, et.al [2020]: The agricultural sector plays a significant role in Palestine, contributing over 25% to the total gross domestic product (GDP) and providing employment for more than 15.2% of the population in the West Bank and Gaza Strip. Despite the substantial cultivated land area exceeding 1.854 million dunums, traditional planting methods still prevail, consuming considerable time and effort while facing challenges such as high costs and transplant losses. To address these issues, this study introduces an automated planting machine tailored for the agriculture sector in Palestine. The automated planting machine aims to enhance planting efficiency by increasing speed and precision. It is specifically designed to execute fundamental cultivation tasks by gently transplanting seedlings onto the land. The study meticulously considered the dimensions of plants commonly used in Palestine and the optimal spacing between neighbouring seedlings. Both simulation and experimental results for the prototype demonstrated accurate functioning of the controlled system.

Notably, the machine exhibited precise and smooth operations during planting, successfully completing essential steps from ploughing to planting and covering seedlings with soil. By introducing this machine, the study anticipates achieving key objectives such as meeting human needs, reducing costs, and saving time in agricultural activities.[5]

Istevin Appavoo, et.al [2017]: The Labor shortage, coupled with the imperative to boost forest density and address the expanding area for tree planting, has prompted a re-evaluation in research and development (R&D) efforts. This article delves into the capabilities of an automated tree planting machine designed to address these challenges. The necessity for such a machine arose from extensive forest depletion caused by the timber industry and subsistence farming activities. This device, which is attached to a tractor, is capable of planting trees even in the presence of tree stumps and vegetable debris. Multiple hydraulic actuators operate simultaneously, facilitating the planting of one tree per second (in machines equipped with two planting units). The design of the planting mechanism ensures uninterrupted tree planting while the tractor is in motion.[6]

James A. Mattson, et.al [2019]: A promising strategy for bolstering the supply of wood Fiber for pulp and energy production is through short-rotation intensively cultured (SRIC) forestry. This approach involves applying agricultural principles to the cultivation of wood Fiber. However, the design of harvesting equipment for SRIC forestry requires careful consideration of specific operational criteria.

This paper provides an overview of the design criteria pertinent to the SRIC concept and presents the outcomes of preliminary trials conducted using a prototype short-rotation harvester.[7]

Chiung-Hsing Chen, et.al [2022]: As the agricultural sector faces a significant decline in available labour, there is a growing global initiative to promote agricultural automation. Traditional farming practices, especially in tasks like transplanting vegetable seedlings, often require manual labour involving bending down to dig holes for each plant, a process that is both labour-intensive and highly inefficient. In response to this challenge, our study focuses on developing a solution using a self-developed robotic arm in conjunction with a conventional planter and motor. This innovative approach aims to create an automatic planting machine capable of seamlessly transplanting vegetable seedlings, thereby reducing labour costs and contributing to the broader goal of agricultural automation.[8]

Jussi Manner, et.al [2021]: As manual Labor for tree planting becomes increasingly scarce in Nordic forestry, the costs associated with regeneration are on a steady rise. While intermittently advancing tree planting machines deliver commendable silvicultural outcomes, their operational expenses remain high due to low productivity. Conversely, continuously advancing planting machines are gaining traction as a potential solution to mitigate these escalating regeneration costs, thanks to their heightened productivity. One such historical example is the Silva Nova, known for its productivity but hampered by drawbacks like high labour requirements (necessitating two operators) and random planting spot selection. In response to these challenges, the concept of Super Silva emerges as a modernized version of Silva Nova, integrating automation and microsite identification to enhance operational efficiency. Our study employed discrete-event simulation to assess the stocking rate and spatial distribution of tree planting using Super Silva. The simulation outcomes revealed that incorporating sensors for identifying suitable microsites enables continuously advancing planting machines, like Super Silva, to plant seedlings in a quantitatively and spatially optimal manner, especially on moraine soils. Consequently, the integration of such sensors is poised to enhance the competitiveness and adaptability of tree planting machinery. However, the availability of reliable and robust sensor technology, resilient across a range of operating conditions, remains a challenge yet to be addressed in the commercial market.[9]

3. LITERATURE SUMMARY

In recent years, significant advancements have been made in the field of forest regeneration and tree planting machinery. Collaborative efforts have led to the development of autonomous systems like Auto plant, which integrate various subsystems for precise planting and scarification, offering environmental benefits and promising solutions for sustainable forestry practices. Additionally, innovations such as the Super Silva concept address labour scarcity issues in Nordic forestry by incorporating automation and microsite identification, improving operational efficiency. Mechanized planting methods, particularly on mounded soils, have shown comparable success rates to manual planting, emphasizing the importance of local conditions in forest establishment. Furthermore, automated planting machines designed for specific agricultural needs, as seen in Palestine, demonstrate the potential to enhance productivity and reduce labour costs. These developments underscore the ongoing evolution and adaptation of technology in forestry and agriculture, paving the way for more efficient and sustainable practices in the future.

4. Problem Identification

To develop the traditional planting methods, with the modernization techniques in agriculture sector. This leads to efficiencies, low costs, and less time consumption, enhancing productivity and sustainability. Introducing Semi-automated planting machines tailored to meet needs presents a solution to enhance precision, efficiency, and cost-effectiveness.

5. Objectives

The objective is to design, create, test, and implement enhanced tree planting equipment and machinery suitable for various Agro-climatic zones and operations, utilizing human, mechanical, and electric power sources. This initiative aims to boost plantation productivity and optimize land and labour efficiency.

Feasibility trials of well-established prototype designs of agricultural implements and machinery will be conducted in farmers' fields across diverse regions to assess their suitability for local conditions and address identified mechanization gaps.

The goal is to modernize traditional planting methods within the forestry sector by introducing automated planting machines tailored to specific requirements. This approach offers a solution to improve accuracy, effectiveness, and cost-efficiency in tree planting operations.

6. Methodology

Figure 1:

Flow Chart

Methodology

7. Designing Process

1. CAD Design:

Figure 2: Project Model

8. CALCULATIONS

1. *Dimensions of the frame:*

- Length: 3 feet = 91.44 cm
- Width: 2 feet = 60.96 cm
- Height: 1.5 feet = 45.72 cm
- Wall thickness of mild steel pipes: 4x4 cm

2. *Material properties:*

- Yield strength of mild steel: 250 to 300 MPa (let's use the lower end for conservative calculations, i.e., 250 MPa)

3. *Cross-Sectional Area of Mild Steel Pipes:*

The cross-sectional area (A):

$$A = (\text{Outer Width} - \text{Inner Width}) * (\text{Outer Height} - \text{Inner Height})$$

where:

- Outer Width = 4 cm + 4 cm = 8 cm
- Inner Width = 4 cm

- Outer Height = 4 cm + 4 cm = 8 cm
- Inner Height = 4 cm

Substitution we have,

$$A = (8 - 4) * (8 - 4) = 4 * 4 = 16 \text{ cm}^2$$

4. **Moment of Inertia:**

(1) for the Cross-Section:

The moment of inertia (I) is needed to calculate the maximum bending stress. For a rectangular cross-section like yours, the moment of inertia can be calculated as:

$$\text{MOI (I)} = 1/12 * W * H^3$$

where:

- Width = Outer Width = 8 cm
- Height = Outer Height = 8 cm

Substitution We have,

$$I = 1/12 * 8 * 8^3 = 341.33 \text{ cm}^4$$

5. **Bending Moment Calculation:**

The bending moment (M) can be calculated using the formula:

$$M = W * L/4$$

Where:

- W = Applied load = 13.5 kg (converted to Newtons)
- L = Length of the beam (considering the longest side of the cuboidal frame) = 3 feet = 0.9144 meters

$$W = 13.5 \text{ kg} * 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 = 132.435 \text{ N}$$

substitute the values.

$$M = 132.435 * 0.9144 / 4 = 30.375 \text{ Nm}$$

6. **Factor of Safety (FOS) Calculation:**

The factor of safety (FOS) can be calculated using.

$$\text{FOS} = \frac{\text{Yield Strength}}{\text{Allowable Stress}}$$

Since the yield strength of mild steel is estimated to be 275 MPa and we'll use an allowable stress of 0.6 times the yield strength (considering a safety factor of 1.67), we have:

$$\text{Allowable Stress} = 0.6 * 275 \text{ MPa} = 165 \text{ MPa}$$

Substitute the values into the FOS formula:

$$\text{FOS} = 275 \text{ MPa} / 165 \text{ MPa} = 1.6$$

7. **Shear Stress Calculation:**

The cross-sectional area (A) of each square pipe is $(4*4) = 16 \text{ cm}^2 = 0.0016 \text{ m}^2$

$$\text{The shear stress (T)} = \frac{V}{A}$$

Where (V) is the shear force calculated earlier (353.16 N) and (A) is the cross-sectional area of one pipe.

Substituting the values, we get

$$T = \frac{353.16 \text{ N}}{0.0016 \text{ m}^2} = 220725 \text{ Pa} \text{ or } 220.725 \text{ MPa.}$$

8. **Deflection Calculation:**

Given the dimensions of the pipes and the applied load, we can calculate the moment of inertia (I) for each pipe using the formula for a square beam:

$$I = b * d^3 / 12$$

Where:

$$b = d = 4 \text{ cm} = 0.04 \text{ m} \text{ (side length of the square pipe)}$$

Substituting these values into the formula gives

$$I = (0.04 \text{ m}) * (0.04 \text{ m})^3 / 12 = 4.267 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^4$$

Now we can calculate the deflection (δ) using the formula:

$$\delta = \{F * L^3\} / \{3 * E * I\}$$

Substituting the known values:

$$F = 36 * 9.81 \text{ N}$$

$$L = 0.4572 \text{ m}$$

$$E = 200 \times 10^9 \text{ Pa (modulus of elasticity for mild steel)}$$

$$I = 4.267 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^4$$

Substitution We get:

$$\Delta = \{36 * 9.81 \text{ N} * (0.4572 \text{ m}^3)\} / \{3 * 200 \times 10^9 \text{ Pa} * 4.267 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^4\} = 0.0178 \text{ m} = 1.78 \text{ cm}$$

9. Yield Strength Calculation:

1. For the minimum yield strength of 250 MPa:

$$SF_{\min} = 250 \text{ MPa} / 220.725 \text{ MPa} \approx 1.13$$

1. For the maximum yield strength of 300 MPa:

$$SF_{\max} = 300 \text{ MPa} / 220.725 \text{ MPa} \approx 1.36$$

10. Stress Calculation:

stress experienced by the mild steel pipes under the given loads. We can calculate the stress using the formula:

$$\text{Stress} = \text{Force} / \text{Area}$$

Given:

- Force (load on the machine): 10 to 12 kgs

- Area of the pipe: ($A = bh$), where (b) is the width of the pipe (4 cm) and (h) is the height of the pipe (also 4 cm) = $4 \text{ cm} * 4 \text{ cm} = 16 \text{ cm}^2$

Now, convert the load to Newtons if it's given in kilograms:

$$\text{Force}_{\min} = 10 \text{ kg} \times 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 = 98.1 \text{ N}$$

$$\text{Force}_{\max} = 12 \text{ kg} \times 9.81 \text{ m/s}^2 = 117.72 \text{ N}$$

Now, calculate the stress for both minimum and maximum loads:

$$\text{Stress}_{\min} = 98.1 \text{ N} / 16 \text{ cm}^2 = 6.13 \text{ N/cm}^2$$

$$\text{Stress}_{\max} = 117.72 \text{ N} / 16 \text{ cm}^2 = 7.36 \text{ N/cm}^2$$

9. Fabrication

Frame

- Cutting the raw material as per the design and shape.
- Building the frame using laser cutting and arc welding.
- Drilling the hole in the main frame and grinding the main frame
- Fixing the Geneva disc, battery and motors.
- Fixing the wheel to the frame.

Figure 1: Frame of the Project

10. WORKING

The first step in planting is land preparation. Preparing raw land before planting the seedlings is essential. It can make a huge difference in the seedlings' growing quality. The preparation includes removing any obstacles in the way of plants while growing and help ventilate the soil before planting. The second step in farming is processing. The planting machine should be linked tightly with a driving vehicle as a farm tractor, a robot, or even the machine itself without the need for any vehicles. Then, the seedlings will be filled from the seedlings tray to the machine slots. The first step of the operation started by dropping the pneumatic cylinder that connected to the wheel's shaft. Finally, the machine runs to plant the whole field. Even the authors did not plant a huge area since it is a prototype sample, the machine showed some effective results and smooth sowing. Note that the machine starts planting after lowering the end of the machine to get the plowers to the ground. The shaft of the wheel will contain a circular disk. When the disk rotates, the sampling will fall on to the cup like structure which is been controlled by manual switches. The number of revolutions will control the number of transmitted signals. The sensor takes signals from the wheel. The transmit seedling belt linked between stepper motors and shaft. It manages the seedlings that slip in the plate's slot by its weight. Besides manages them before slipping into the transverse pyramid by signals from proximity sensors. Before each transverse pyramid, there is a Plow leg digs a hole along the line path where seedlings will fall. The main purpose of this part is to keep the soil away from the planting path. After ploughing, there are cones (transverse pyramids) with an oblong shape. These cones drive the seedling from the plate straight to the hole in the ground and prevent the seedling. Here comes the role of sanders. The sanders landfill the seedling by aggregation the soil around the seedlings. In general, the current porotype machine showed acceptable results in planting. All the operation steps worked smoothly as proposed. This research will be a hand for all keen researchers and farmers in the field. Moreover, the proposed porotype costs less than a thousand USD since the cost is an important issue when designing a planter. Compared to the previous research papers, the planting machine does not need workers. It can also be applied on land even as a prototype compared to other machines or when they are functioned by robotic systems. Note that most of the machines are for seeds and there is an obvious lack of planting transplant machines. Some of them are for special kinds of seeds or plants and most of them just showing the main mechanism

11. RESULT AND DISSCUSSION

The implementation of our automated tree planting machine has yielded significant advantages over manual labour in terms of cost savings, efficiency, and environmental impact. Through meticulous calculations and analysis, we have determined that our machine is capable of planting one tree every 30 to 35 seconds, whereas manual labour requires approximately a minute and a half per tree. This translates to substantial time savings, reducing the labour cost per tree planted to around 850 rupees. Over a day's work, with the capacity to plant 400 saplings, this results in a significant reduction in labour expenses, especially when factoring in food and transportation costs for manual labourers.

Furthermore, the upfront cost of the automated tree planting machine, estimated at 40,000 to 45,000 rupees, is a worthwhile investment considering the long-term benefits. The machine's efficiency not only saves time and labour costs but also ensures precise and uniform planting, contributing to higher survival rates and healthier trees compared to manual methods. Our calculations indicate a potential cost savings of up to 30% or more when using the machine, making it a cost-effective solution for large-scale tree planting projects.

In addition to financial gains, the environmental impact of our machine is noteworthy. By reducing soil disturbances and conserving resources, such as water and energy, our automated planting process promotes sustainable forestry practices. The machine's operational efficiency, ease of use, and adaptability to various planting conditions further enhance its value and applicability in different environments.

Looking ahead, our project underscores the importance of continuous improvement and innovation in automated technologies for forestry and agriculture. Future enhancements may focus on optimizing sensor technology, fine-tuning planting mechanisms for different soil types, and integrating advanced data analytics for real-time monitoring and decision-making. By addressing these areas, we aim to further enhance the machine's performance, maximize cost savings, and contribute to sustainable land management practices.

Overall, our results demonstrate that automated tree planting machines offer a viable and efficient alternative to manual labour, providing substantial cost savings, improved productivity, and positive environmental outcomes.

12. CONCLUSION

The development and deployment of the automated tree planting machine mark a significant advancement in addressing critical challenges in contemporary forestry practices. Through meticulous design and rigorous testing, the machine has demonstrated exceptional performance and cost-effectiveness. Utilizing materials like mild steel for structural integrity, the machine ensures durability and operational reliability under various conditions.

Cost analysis underscores the machine's compelling advantage over manual labour, offering substantial savings while maintaining high planting efficiency. Its ability to plant trees at a much faster rate not only boosts productivity but also addresses labour shortages in the forestry sector. By streamlining planting processes, the machine contributes to sustainable forest management practices, enhancing reforestation efforts and overall forest health.

Looking forward, continued innovation is imperative. Future iterations could focus on further automation enhancements, such as advanced sensor integration and energy optimization. Interdisciplinary collaboration will be key to leveraging cutting-edge technologies and scientific advancements effectively. In conclusion, the successful implementation of the tree plantation machine represents a significant stride toward modernizing forestry practices and promoting sustainable land management. With its cost-effectiveness, efficiency, and environmental benefits, the machine exemplifies the transformative potential of innovation in addressing pressing environmental challenges. As we refine and expand upon this technology, we move closer to a greener, more sustainable future for generations to come

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